

Supplementary Table 3. Core microbiome of three reactor types.

Samples	Number	Genus
CSTR & PFR & UASBD	14	Defluviitoga Uncultured Dethiobacteraceae Caldicoprobacter Methanosarcina Syntrophaceticus DTU014 Proteiniphilum Tepidimicrobium Tepidanaerobacter Petrimonas Acetomicrobium Limnochordia Tissierella MBA03
CSTR & PFR	5	Corynebacterium Lentimicrobium Defluviitalea Dethiobacter UCG-012
PFR & UASBD	3	Pelotomaculum Fastidiosipila Fermentimonas
CSTR & UASBD	2	Aminobacterium Romboutsia
PFR	20	Ruminococcus Candidatus Caldatribacterium Unknown Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales Ruminiclostridium UCG-010 Chelativorans Uncultured Anaerovoracaceae Irregularibacter Hungateiclostridiaceae Uncultured Desulfotomaculales Unknown Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales Uncultured Firmicutes M55-D21 Unknown Clostridia Sedimentibacter Uncultured Erysipelotrichaceae HN-HF0106 Methanoculleus MSB-5E12 Clostridium sensu stricto
CSTR	1	Desulfitibacter
UASBD	6	Propioniciclava Thermovirga Gallicola Unknown Halobacterota Bacteroidales UCG-001 D8A-2